

USING PIRLS ASSIGNMENTS WHEN WORKING ON A STORY TEXT

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Abstract. *This article discusses the effectiveness of using PIRLS tasks, one of the international assessment programs, in developing students' skills in working with text in primary education. In particular, it examines ways to develop higher-level thinking competencies such as understanding, analysis, comparison, and drawing conclusions in students based on narrative texts. The article provides methodological recommendations for the structure of PIRLS tasks, their types (questions and answers, tests, open questions), and their integration into the teaching process. During the study, it was observed that students' logical thinking and ability to react to the text increased when working with narrative texts. The article also provides practical recommendations for teachers on using PIRLS tasks in assessing students' literacy.*

Keywords: *PIRLS, narrative text, working with text, primary education, academic literacy, tasks, methodology, analysis, reading competence, teaching technologies.*

Introduction. In today's globalization process, improving the quality and efficiency of education, assessing students' knowledge based on international standards is becoming increasingly important. Especially at the primary education stage, the formation of students' reading literacy is one of the urgent tasks. Therefore, the development of students' skills in working with text based on international assessment programs, including the PIRLS (Progress in International Reading Literacy Study) system, is recognized as one of the important directions of reforms in the field of education.

In one of his speeches on education, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.M.Mirziyoyev said: "To build a new Uzbekistan, first of all, we need to raise a young generation that is educated, thoughtful and modern" [2]. This idea is based on the need to organize the educational process based on advanced international experiences.

Also, the "Development Strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026" and the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-60 dated January 28, 2022 "On Priority Areas for the Development of Science and Innovation" set out measures to introduce international assessment criteria in the field of education and improve the functional literacy of students.

Literature analysis. The issue of developing students' reading literacy, in particular, the development of skills in working with text, is one of the topical issues of attention of domestic and foreign researchers. Uzbek scientists, including M.Q. Kholmatova, D.Y. Kadirova, Z.S. Mamatova and others, have conducted scientific research on the role of modern pedagogical approaches in developing reading and analysis skills of primary school students. In particular, the research of M.Q. Kholmatova and D.A. Utanbayeva sheds light on the impact of teaching technologies based on text analysis on students' thinking [7].

In international experience, within the framework of the PIRLS assessment program, students are tested for such competencies as understanding the text, distinguishing the main idea, and responding to the author's opinion. PIRLS tasks are mainly based on literary (story, fairy tale)

and informational (article, news) texts. Their focus on finding answers to questions based on the text the student has read, re-expressing and evaluating the information they have understood is reflected in many foreign studies, in particular in the work conducted by Mullis I.V. and Martin M.O. [8].

The methodological foundations of the tasks developed within the framework of PIRLS, the criteria for formulating questions, and the system for assessing students' answers are a convenient platform for use in pedagogical practice. This is also covered in detail in the “Methodological Guide for Preparing for International Studies” published by the Education Inspectorate of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2021 [7].

Also, the methodological recommendations on “Integrating PIRLS tasks into primary school lessons” compiled step by step by A. Rasulova and N. Egamkulova emphasize that combining methods such as question-and-answer, cluster, insert, and “spectrum of thoughts” when working on narrative texts is practically effective.

In modern pedagogy, PIRLS tasks serve as a powerful tool for developing students' skills such as forming independent thinking, analyzing the text they have read, and drawing conclusions. Therefore, it is important to deeply study the scientific, theoretical and practical foundations for the effective use of these tasks in working with primary school students.

Research methodology. This study aims to study the effectiveness of using PIRLS tasks in the process of developing skills in working with narrative text in primary school students. The following scientific methods were used during the study:

1. Theoretical analysis method. Existing literature, methodological guides, scientific articles and government documents on the content, structure and form of tasks of the PIRLS international assessment program were studied. Local and foreign studies on primary education were analyzed.

2. Empirical methods. During the experiment, students were given PIRLS-type tasks based on narrative text and their results were evaluated.

3. Observation and interview method. During the lesson, students' attitude to the tasks, level of thinking, and answers to questions were monitored by the teacher and observer, and clarifications were made through interviews.

The results of the students in the experimental group were compared with those of students who received education based on the traditional method, the advantages of PIRLS tasks were identified, and general conclusions were drawn. Based on the results of the study, it was proven that the use of PIRLS tasks is an effective tool for developing competencies such as text comprehension, main idea identification, logical connection, and critical thinking in students.

Analysis and Results. The International Association for the Evaluation of Educational Achievement (IEA) PIRLS study (Primary International Reading Literacy Study) was launched in 2001 as an extension of the Association's 1991 reading literacy research program.

Because reading literacy development is so important to every student's growth, education, and daily life, the International Association for the Evaluation of Educational Achievement (IEA) has been systematically assessing students' reading comprehension skills internationally for nearly 60 years, and is working to create the necessary conditions for them to learn to read. This association (IEA) is an independent international organization consisting of government agencies and national research institutes that conducts international comparative analysis of educational achievements since the 1960s in order to gain a deeper understanding of educational reforms in participating countries with different education systems [11].

Each PIRLS assessment study continues this tradition of conducting a series of surveys for parents or guardians, schools, teachers, countries, and students, and of conducting a modern analysis of changes in student reading achievement. Survey data on students' learning and educational opportunities provide important information for interpreting the results. The first two sections of the PIRLS 2021 assessment framework are the PIRLS 2021 Reading Literacy Framework and the PIRLS 2021 Questionnaire Framework. The Reading Literacy Framework assesses the reading comprehension of primary school students based on two main goals of students' reading comprehension: to gain artistic experience and to obtain and use information, and four comprehension processes (finding, inferring, integrating, and evaluating). The framework covers topics from the PIRLS 2021 questionnaires. The third section provides information about the assessment criteria for the PIRLS 2021 international study. Over the past 20 years, the PIRLS study, which assesses students' reading comprehension levels, has been combined with PIRLS questionnaire data on the environments that facilitate students' development of reading comprehension skills, providing researchers with valuable information on improving students' reading literacy around the world [11].

During the study, pilot lessons using PIRLS-format tasks based on a narrative text were conducted with the participation of 4th grade students. The lessons included tasks such as understanding the content of the text, identifying the main idea, organizing the sequence of events, and reacting to the actions of the characters. The following aspects were observed according to the work performed by the students:

1. The ability to understand the text and distinguish the main idea increased.

Questions based on PIRLS tasks encouraged students to read the text carefully and to understand the essence in depth. 85 percent of students in the experimental group were able to correctly identify the main idea of the story content, compared to 60 percent in the control group.

2. Critical thinking and evaluation skills were developed.

Through open-ended questions, students were asked to express their opinions about the actions of the characters and suggest alternative endings. As a result, students learned to express their personal attitude to the text.

3. Independent work and reflection activities became more active.

PIRLS tasks developed students' ability to increase their thinking activity, make independent decisions, and provide well-founded answers to questions. In the experimental group, 70% of students were able to provide well-founded and complete answers to questions.

4. Reading and writing skills developed harmoniously.

Text-based written expression tasks (for example, writing a conclusion, continuing the story) improved students' not only reading, but also written speech.

5. Interest in the lessons increased.

Most students were interested in working on the basis of the story text and thinking about the lives of the characters. This, in turn, made their participation in the lesson more active.

Story text on from PIRLS tasks at work use mechanism

PIRLS task type	Purpose	Story text with at work application
Information definition (Literal)	From the text clear and clear information find	" Hero " to the students who " What happened ?", " The incident" where like " was it ?" questions is given

PIRLS task type	Purpose	Story text with at work application
Understanding analysis to do	In the text events , cause and effect their dependencies understanding	" What for hero this the work " did it ?" or " As a result? " what face " gave ?" questions with work
Interpretation to do (Interpretive)	In the text hidden meaning or author intention understanding	The hero's feelings or author's main message explanation tasks
Evaluation and idea to inform	Student's to the text personal attitude expression to grow	" You this to the event how attitude " Do you mean this story ?" or "This story to you what taught ?"
Contextual analysis	Text structure and methodological tools analysis to do	In the text metaphor , simile , figurative tools determination tasks
Text again work	Read to the text based on new idea , scenario , ending create	" The story other the end write " , " Hero himself different will catch what it would be ?"

In general, the results of the pilot study showed that PIRLS tasks are effective in developing students' knowledge, skills, and competencies when working with narrative texts. The use of such tasks when working with texts activates students, directs them to critical and creative thinking, and forms the skills of independent reading and analysis.

Conclusions and recommendations. The results of the above study show that the use of PIRLS tasks when working with narrative texts significantly develops reading literacy, comprehension, analysis, and response skills of primary school students. Through such tasks, students learn to think independently, logically connect the chain of events, evaluate the content of the text, and draw reasonable conclusions.

PIRLS tasks, with their richness of content, question system, and assessment criteria, serve to expand students' thinking. They also actively involve them in the reading process, and make it possible to organize lessons in an interesting and effective way. The positive results obtained from the experiment have shown the need for widespread use of these tasks.

Recommendations:

1. Primary school teachers should regularly use PIRLS task formats (multiple choice tests, open-ended questions, and essay tasks).
2. It is advisable to include tasks in the curriculum that serve to develop functional reading and thinking based on narrative texts.
3. Methodological guides and lesson plans should give ample space to sample tasks developed based on PIRLS approaches.
4. When assessing students' knowledge, it is necessary to take into account not only traditional questions, but also tasks aimed at expressing their thoughts and personal opinions.
5. It is recommended to organize advanced training courses for teachers based on PIRLS tasks.

Enriching the educational process through PIRLS tasks and forming students' reading competencies in line with modern requirements remains one of the priority goals of the New Uzbekistan education system.

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